

THRIVING TOWARDS DRUG-FREE COMMUNITIES: WORK LIFE OF AGENTS OF PHILIPPINE DRUG ENFORCEMENT AGENCY (PDEA)

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the work life of the Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency (PDEA) agents which specifically delved into the experiences of the informants, how the informants addressed the challenges encountered and the aspirations of the informants to improve the performance of their duties. This study is a qualitative type of research using the phenomenological approach that utilized ten (10) informants from the PDEA Bohol Provincial Office in Tagbilaran City, using a validated interview guide with open-ended questions prepared by the researcher. The informants were all interviewed individually. Colaizzi's analysis was used to analyze the data collected. Three themes summarized the positive experiences of the informants, namely: Disrupting Drug Activities, Sense of Accomplishment, and Strong Organizational Support System. As to the negative experiences, the themes revealed were Life-Endangering Threats, Work-Related Struggles and Setbacks, and Pressure of Uncertainty. The themes Strategic Work Balance, Strengthening Intelligence Gathering, and Resilience and Strong Determination highlighted addressing the challenges encountered. Moreover, the themes: Career Advancement and Enhanced Compensation and Resources, described their aspirations. The PDEA should be empowered to be more effective in combatting drug problem by enhancing their training programs, improve agents' welfare, and increase financial support for the agency's operations.

Keywords: *Agents, Work Life, Drug-Free Communities, Challenges, Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency*

INTRODUCTION

The drug problem has been a persistent issue globally. Task forces have been created by numerous jurisdictions as a strategic response to address targeted crime issues within law enforcement, such as drug crimes and organized crime. These task forces offer a surgical approach, effectively minimizing redundant efforts, promoting rational and coherent crime-solving methods, and optimizing the utilization of limited resources (Meliton, 2016).

Despite the intensive fight against drugs, according to the World Drug Report (United Nations [UN], 2023), illicit drug supply and increasingly agile trafficking networks are compounding intersecting global crises and challenging health services and law enforcement responses. In 2022, approximately 7 million individuals had formal interactions with the police, such as arrests, cautions, or warnings related to drug offenses, with roughly two-thirds of these cases involving drug use or possession for personal use. Additionally, 2.7 million people were prosecuted for drug offenses, and more than 1.6 million were convicted worldwide in the same year. However, the criminal justice responses to drug offenses varied significantly across different regions (United Nations [UN], 2024).

Meanwhile, in its efforts to address the drug problem, the Philippine government has instituted various programs, including the sustained enforcement effort against illegal drugs, which has been ongoing for several years. The Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency (PDEA) was established by Republic Act No. 9165, also known as The Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002, to enforce the law of all the provisions efficiently and effectively on dangerous drugs and/or precursors and essential chemicals, as provided in R.A. No. 9165 (Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency [PDEA], n.d.). As the lead agency in the nation's fight against the drug crisis, the Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency (PDEA) shoulders the responsibility for spearheading efforts to combat the drug menace in the country. It is responsible for preventing, investigating, and combating any dangerous drugs, controlled precursors, and essential chemicals.

According to the latest figures from PDEA's drug campaign data, from July 1, 2022, to February 29, 2024, a total of 5,691 high-value targets (HVTs) were apprehended. In addition, authorities arrested 84,291 individuals involved in illegal drug activities through 61,800 operations, resulting in the dismantling of 901 drug dens and a shabu laboratory. The seized contraband amounted to PHP32.44 billion, including 4,353.81 kg of shabu, 50.51 kg of cocaine, 54,016 pieces of ecstasy tablets, and 3,589.08 kg of marijuana (Philippine News Agency [PNA], 2024).

On the other hand, the Bohol province has recently seen a surge in drug-related activity, posing a significant challenge for PDEA Bohol along with the other national government agencies. Various operations have been made in the province of Bohol in 2023 and from January 1 to March 6, 2024, led to the confiscation of shabu worth at least P172.7 million (Cebu Daily News [CDN], 2024). According to PDEA Bohol, individuals of

high value are involved in the distribution of illegal drugs within the province and its neighboring areas (The Bohol Tribune, 2024).

The attitudes of narcotics officers toward drugs and drug enforcement are unknown variables that almost certainly impact and influence front-line drug officers. Petrocelli et al. (2014) underscored the importance of understanding officers' attitudes toward drugs and enforcement, which can influence their actions and discretion. On the other hand, Laila (2021) discusses the role of the police in combating narcotics crimes, emphasizing the need for comprehensive legal regulations and the challenges posed by legal, law enforcement, and cultural factors.

The challenges faced by drug enforcement agents in the Philippines are multifaceted and deeply entrenched in the country's social, political, and economic landscape. The government's aggressive war on drugs, characterized by extrajudicial killings and human rights abuses, has been widely criticized (Lamchek & Jopson, 2024).

While the headlines often focus on high-profile raids and casualties, a crucial yet unseen element lies within the Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency (PDEA), its agents. Extensive research has documented the experiences of drug surrenderees and police officers in the fight against illegal drugs. Notable studies include Lived Experiences of Philippine National Police Drug Enforcers in the Eastern Visayas Region (Noble, 2024), Lived Experiences of Police Officers in the Implementation of Operational Plan Against Illegal Drugs (Fuentes et al., 2023), and Experiences of Drug Surrenderees in Highly Urbanized Cities in Cebu: A Phenomenological Study (Damuag et al., 2024). However, a critical gap remains in understanding the work life of PDEA agents, who are at the forefront of the anti-drug campaign, and who perform a complex and dangerous role that has received little attention.

This study generally sought to explore the life work of Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency agents, particularly in the performance of their duty, how the informants address the challenges encountered, and the informants' aspirations to improve their performance. This approach allowed them to contribute to discussions and initiatives aimed at improving their working conditions, professional development, and overall quality of life. This study was also essential for informing evidence-based policies, strategies, and training programs tailored to the unique needs and contexts of PDEA agents.

Research Questions

This study explored the work life of the Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency (PDEA) Agents, Province of Bohol, Philippines.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of the informants in the performance of their duties?

2. How do the informants address the challenges encountered in the performance of their duties?
3. What are the aspirations of the informants to improve the performance of their duties?

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted in Bohol, Philippines. Purposive sampling was utilized as participants were deliberately selected based on their experience. This involved ten (10) informants whom seven (7) were male and the other three (3) were female who disclosed their work experiences as agents of the Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency in the PDEA Bohol Provincial Office who have at least 3 years of experience as agents and have participated in anti-narcotic operations.

The researcher crafted and used an interview guide in conducting in-depth interviews, aimed to uncover the work life of the informants. This guide underwent rigorous validation processes, including review by the adviser, the panel of experts, and the graduate school dean. It included informed consent procedures to formally invite participants and ensured their voluntary and unrestricted provision of information crucial to achieving the research objectives. The first part of the interview guide explored the informants' work lives during their duties, including their positive and negative experiences. The second part delved into how the informants addressed the challenges encountered, and the third part explored their aspirations to improve their duties.

The data collection method that was used in this research was an in-depth interview in order to extract precise data addressing the sub-problems. To maintain accurate records, the researcher utilized an audio recorder during the interviews, and the recordings were transcribed verbatim before analysis. The data gathered from the informants during the in-depth interview was analyzed through Collaizi's 7 steps of data analysis. The responses of the participants during the interview were transcribed and translated individually. From the interview transcriptions, significant statements were extracted and core meanings were formulated. The formulated meanings with commonalities or common key ideas were then grouped into clustered themes.

RESULTS

The following eleven (11) emergent themes were developed to provide a clearer understanding of the work life of the Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency (PDEA) Agents.

Research Questions	Emergent Themes
I. Experiences of the Informants during the Performance of Their Duties	
A. Positive Experiences:	1. Disrupting Drug Activities

	2. Sense of Accomplishment
	3. Strong Organizational Support System
B. Negative Experiences:	1. Life-Endangering Threats
	2. Work-Related Struggles and Setbacks
	3. Pressure of Uncertainty
II. Addressing the Challenges Encountered by the Informants in the Performance of Their Duties	
	1. Strategic Work Balance
	2. Strengthening Intelligence Gathering
	3. Resilience and Strong Determination
III. Aspirations of the Informants to Improve the Performance of Their Duties	
	1. Career Advancement
	2. Enhanced Compensation and Resources

DISCUSSION

I. Experiences of the Informants During the Performance of Their Duties

A. Positive Experiences:

1. Disrupting Drug Activities: This theme unravels how informants felt proud and fulfilled when they did their job effectively. The majority of them shared that their most memorable experiences were during successful anti-drug operations. The informants felt a strong sense of purpose and pride, knowing their work helped protect people and made their communities safer.

Informant 1 mentioned that:

When I started my duty, Ma'am, when I entered the agency, and, you know, Ma'am, being able to arrest big-time or well-known drug lords, especially during my first operation in 2019, which was the biggest syndicate in Tubigon, Bohol, where I was the

arresting officer. I told myself that I really overcame the challenge and was able to do it (ID11:SS2).

Disrupting Drug Activities aligns closely with Two-Factor theory of Herzberg (1959) which posits that achievement was a key motivator that significantly contributed to job satisfaction. The nature of their work, combating drug trafficking and enforcing drug laws provided ample opportunities for them to experience a sense of accomplishment. Successful operations, such as dismantling drug syndicates or seizing large quantities of illegal substances, not only fulfill their professional duties but also reinforce their commitment to public service.

When informants feel that their efforts lead to tangible results, it could create a positive feedback loop, motivating them to strive for even greater success. This motivation is vital in high-stress environments like law enforcement, where the stakes are high and the challenges are significant. The recognition of their achievements by peers and superiors can further amplify this effect, which leads to higher morale and increased productivity. Harter (1978) which asserts that individuals are motivated to engage in tasks successfully navigate where they perceive themselves as competent.

2. Sense of Accomplishment: Many of the informants expressed feelings of fulfillment in performing their duties, satisfaction in protecting the youth and the whole community, reducing crime, and contentment in achieving justice. Despite the risks of their work dealing with high-profile drug syndicates and combating the spread of illegal drugs, the informants found meaning in their efforts.

Informant 8 stated that:

Well, the fact that you are serving the public and catering to the safety, health, and welfare of the general public is a great task that we are doing so. Ah, it is not only an ordinary service to the public because, at the same time, we are also putting ourselves in great danger, but it is an utmost satisfaction on our part to have served the public (ID18:SS11).

Sense of Accomplishment theme aligns closely with the principles of Two-Factor theory of Herzberg (1959) which explains that motivators are intrinsic elements related to the nature of the work itself, such as achievement, recognition, responsibility, and opportunities for personal growth. When employees engage in tasks that they perceive as meaningful and impactful such as providing services that enhance public safety and welfare, they experience a profound sense of fulfillment.

The informants perceive their contributions as significant such as helping to dismantle drug den, they experienced a profound sense of fulfillment. The sense of happiness this has given them enhanced their feelings of competence and belonging, reinforcing their motivation to continue. Moreover, the knowledge that their actions contributed positively to the community's health and safety can be a powerful motivator, that created a sense of purpose in their roles.

3. Strong Organizational Support System: Supportive practices at PDEA contribute to a positive work environment by helping the informants feel valued and motivated. These practices encourage growth, improve morale, and strengthen team effectiveness, which leads to greater job satisfaction and better performance within the agency.

Informant 8 said that:

Well, we always have this career advancement provided by our agency. And every year we have different trainings, advanced trainings so that we will be more specialized and updated in our approach in combating illegal drugs (IDI8:SS69).

Strong Organizational Support System is closely aligned to the principles of Team Performance theory. This theory emphasizes the critical role of guidance and support from senior colleagues in enhancing both team effectiveness and individual fulfillment within a collaborative work environment. According to this theory, effective teamwork is characterized by several key elements, including clearly defined roles, collaborative efforts, and a shared focus on common goals (Humphrey et al., 2009).

Senior colleagues who consistently support and guide their junior counterparts play a key role in creating an environment that encourages professional growth. The helpful feedback and assisting agents in learning from their mistakes, these senior colleagues not only improve individual skills but also strengthen the team as a whole.

According to Hackman (2002), for teams to be effective, they need a clear and motivating direction, along with a structure that promotes collaboration and personal development. Additionally, encouragement from senior colleagues helps create an environment of open communication and constructive feedback, which is essential for ongoing learning and progress within the team (Gadirajurrett et al., 2018).

B. Negative Experiences:

1. Life-Endangering Threats: This theme emphasized the serious dangers the informants faced in their line of work, which could put both their safety and their families at risk.

Informant 1 recalled that:

This, Ma'am, is really a tough part of being an agent, especially when we encounter high-profile individuals, like well-known drug lords. I've experienced this myself. I've received intense death threats, especially when they manage to get hold of our number. It's even worse when we're about to file a case because some people recognize us. Naturally, the family of the accused will show up, as they usually do during the filing of cases (IDI1:SS154).

The theme *Life-Endangering Threats* closely aligns with the principles of Competence Motivation theory that emphasizes the importance of socio-emotional support in fostering competence. If personnel do not receive adequate emotional backing from their peers or superiors during high-risk operations, their ability to perceive themselves as competent may diminish further (Harter, 1978).

Death threats directed at the informants and their families, risks associated with dealing with unknown individuals, and pressures from high-value drug personalities weakened their competence. These stressors led to anxiety and a lessened sense of control, which negatively impacted their motivation and engagement in their roles.

The constant presence of death threats creates a dangerous environment that affects not only the agents but also their families, leading to feelings of helplessness and anxiety about their safety. The mental strain from these threats can make agents lose confidence in their ability to handle dangerous situations, which increases their stress and lowers their overall job satisfaction (Tupas, 2019).

2. Work-Related Struggles and Setbacks: This theme captures the informants' experiences with the challenges and obstacles they experienced. Despite their strong desire to perform their duties effectively, various factors hinder their performance.

Informant 1 stated that:

We're really lacking in personnel, gadgets, and vehicles. I hope they can see this and take action to provide more support for us. We're the ones on the ground, we're the ones constantly moving around in the field, but it's difficult with the lack of equipment and personnel (IDI1:SS344).

The theme *Work-Related Struggles and Setbacks* closely align with the principles of Two-Factor theory that suggests that while motivators such as achievement and recognition can enhance job satisfaction, the absence of adequate hygiene factors like reasonable workload and support can lead to dissatisfaction. Employees who often experience significant exhaustion due to demanding workloads and overwork without sufficient compensation or recognition for their efforts may feel overwhelmed and demoralized, leading to burnout and decreased productivity (Herzberg, 1959).

Factors like exhaustion from heavy workloads, low pay, lack of staff, and limited tools or transportation affected some of the informants. Having too few staff puts a lot of pressure on the informants, it was harder for them to do their jobs well and improve their skills. They could not keep up with the demands of their work because they didn't have enough resources or support.

Employees who feel that their salaries do not reflect their workload or the demands of their roles may become disengaged and demotivated. This is particularly relevant in environments where personnel are stretched thin, as inadequate pay coupled with high demands can exacerbate feelings of unfairness and lead to higher turnover rates (Bengfort, 2024). In addition, inadequate tools or resources hinder employees' ability to

perform their jobs effectively, leading to frustration and decreased morale (Engetou, 2017).

3. Pressure of Uncertainty: This theme reflects the emotional and psychological strain experienced by the informants. This pressure arises from the unpredictable nature of their work, where the operations are often fraught with danger and uncertainty. Unlike conventional criminal activities, drug trafficking mimics a business model that is highly adaptive and organized, which makes it challenging for operatives to predict the behaviors and tactics of those drug personalities.

Informant 4 shared that:

Sometimes, Ma'am, there's also fear. You get nervous because you never know what might happen, and God forbid, there are instances when accidents happen or the job turns out badly (P4:SS33).

The *Pressure of Uncertainty* theme relates significantly to the principles of Two-Factor theory posits that hygiene factors are workplace elements necessary to sustain motivation. While they do not create long-term positive satisfaction, their absence or lack can result in dissatisfaction (Herzberg, 1959).

According to Iyer (2022) the absence of adequate hygiene factors can create a stressful environment for employees, resulting in decreased morale and increased anxiety levels regarding their safety and overall job satisfaction. Moreover, stress significantly impacts the critical thinking skills and job performance of law enforcement officers, necessitating resilience promotion training and relaxation techniques to improve overall health and performance (Clingan, 2020).

II. Address the Challenges Encountered by the Informants in the Performance of Their Duties

Based on their responses, three (3) themes were identified and developed that capture the strategies and approaches the informants used to overcome the difficulties in their line of work.

1. Strategic Work Balance: The job of the informants required them to stay focused, positive, and resilient, especially when facing stressful situations. To maintain this mindset, they used different strategies and techniques that helped them stay effective in their roles. These methods are important for their success in operations.

Informant 2 recalled that:

And if we're busy right now because we're making arrests for 24 hours, then tomorrow or the next day we prepare the case, and after that, we file the case. Then, after that, our supervisor will say, 'Alright, you can rest now.' So, there's that. It helps to relieve the stress as well (ID12:SS266).

This theme is supported by the Competence Motivation theory of Harter (1978) which suggests that individuals are motivated by a need to feel competent and effective in their activities. According to this theory, people are driven to engage in tasks where they feel they can develop and demonstrate their skills, leading to increased motivation and performance. This theory emphasizes how individuals or teams manage their skills.

The informants were motivated by the need to be competent at their jobs. They focused on learning and improving their skills to deal with challenges like preparing for trials or managing drug operations. This desire to get better is a way for them to stay motivated, even when tasks are tough or stressful. In addition, in order to maintain their sense of competence, the agents balanced the time and energy they invested in their work with time for recovery. This balance ensured that their motivation to perform at a high level remained strong.

Employees should have access to different coping strategies to manage stress effectively. Methods like mindfulness and relaxation techniques can help reduce stress and improve focus. Mindfulness, in particular, has been found to enhance emotional control and job satisfaction, making it a useful tool for boosting workplace performance (Sutton, 2021).

Jelinek (2024) purports that good time management is essential for boosting work performance. Employees can improve their productivity by organizing their tasks, setting priorities, and making to-do lists.

2. Strengthening Intelligence Gathering. The informants shared that intelligence gathering is a key part of overcoming the challenges they face in the performance of their duties. They mentioned that they underwent extensive training, including intelligence training, to prepare them for real-life operations before officially stepping into their roles.

Informant 8 narrated:

Well, all agents before coming to active duty were all trained. We have been subjected to stressful activities in order to prepare us for the real Macoy (IDI8: SS179).

Strengthening Intelligence Gathering theme relate significantly to the principles of Two-Factor theory which claimed that training acts as a hygienic element by giving informants the tools they need to manage the intricacies of their work, including operational safety, legal issues, and communication. This guarantees they are ready for the demands of their job, which lowers discontent (Herzberg, 1959).

The informants emphasized that this approach is crucial for the success of PDEA operations and for keeping up with the constantly evolving landscape of drug enforcement. The PDEA agents have become more effective in their mission by continuously enhancing their skills through training, fostering strong teamwork, adopting advanced technologies, improving inter-agency collaboration, and reinforcing security

measures. As drug syndicates adapt and evolve, the agency remains steadfast in ensuring that its intelligence capabilities stay ahead in the fight against illegal drugs.

Training programs are essential as they equip informants with the necessary skills and knowledge to navigate their roles effectively, thereby fostering better communication and collaboration within the team. This aligns with findings that emphasize the importance of clear goals and information sharing in improving team performance; when informants are well-trained, they can contribute to a clearer understanding of objectives, which reduces role ambiguity and enhances collective effort towards goal attainment (van der Hoek et al., 2016).

3. Resilience and Strong Determination. The informants shared that faith and prayer were vital sources of strength in their work. They relied on their belief in God for comfort and guidance, seeing themselves as instruments of His will to protect others. Their faith helped them stay focused, make cautious decisions, and trust that God provided the strength and protection needed in their demanding roles.

Informant 8 mentioned:

First of all, we pray that it is my weapon that I trust more than the firearm that I have. I always pray for guidance and everything that I will, the presence of mind and the judgment call that will serve the purpose and not to make adjustments that will have a negative impact instead (IDI8:SS217).

Resilience and Strong Determination relate closely to the principles of Competence Motivation theory which emphasizes that individuals are motivated to engage in activities when they perceive themselves as competent in those activities. This theory ties closely to personal qualities or character strengths such as perseverance, a positive mindset, and resilience that contribute to personal and professional success (Harter, 1959).

Maintaining a positive mindset is vital for PDEA agents who operate under stressful conditions. A positive outlook helped the informants focus on their capabilities, adapt to dynamic situations, and maintain morale, even in the face of failures or setbacks.

Resilience promotion training and relaxation techniques can help officers manage stress and improve overall health (Clingan, 2020). Coping, on the other hand, involves cognitive and behavioral approaches to managing, alleviating, or reducing the stress triggered by challenging events, typically through problem-focused or emotion-focused strategies (Queiros et al., 2020).

III. Aspirations of the Informants to Improve the Performance of Their Duties

1. Career Advancement. The informants recognize that career development is key to improving their performance and achieving their goals. They believed that gaining more knowledge, particularly in legal matters, would help them carry out their duties

effectively and make better decisions. For the informants, professional growth is not just about personal success but also about being more effective in their responsibilities.

Informant 2 narrated that:

For my professional development at PDEA, I really want to pursue law because it would be a big help, especially when we go to court. All of us go to the Regional Trial Court for drug cases. I want to make sure that no one underestimates me, that I have knowledge of the law and I'm well-versed in it (IDI2:SS316).

Career Advancement relates closely to the principles of Two-factor theory which explains that career advancement is considered a motivator because it involves opportunities for personal growth, achievement, and recognition. When employees aspire to advance in their careers, they are seeking not only external rewards such as promotions or pay increases but also intrinsic satisfaction derived from the sense of accomplishment, mastery, and self-improvement. (Herzberg, 1959).

For the informants, career advancement, especially the prospect of becoming lawyers, is also tied to the desire for recognition. They believed that by pursuing law, they would gain professional recognition and credibility, which would boost their confidence in performing their duties, particularly in complex operations.

Law enforcement officers' motivations for career advancement are often driven by personal aspirations for growth and self-improvement. These officers see career progression as a way to not only increase their rank but also enhance their capacity to impact their communities. Career advancement is often viewed as a reflection of personal competence, leading to higher levels of job satisfaction and engagement (Kappeler & Gaines, 2012). When officers perceive that they can move up the ranks, they tend to show greater commitment to their organizations and are less likely to leave the profession (Gerber & O'Neill, 2012).

2. Enhanced Compensation and Resources. The informants have several goals to improve their professional lives and work environment. With better benefits, more learning opportunities, stronger support, and better equipment, they hope to create a better and more productive work atmosphere that helps them do their jobs more effectively.

According to Informant 3:

One thing we hope for is that our hazard pay gets increased because it's very minimal. Some of our colleagues in technical positions have a higher hazard pay than us, even though we're the ones conducting anti-drug operations. It doesn't seem fair that we get less hazard pay when our work is more dangerous (IDI3:SS348).

The theme *Enhanced Compensation and Resources* connect to Two-Factor theory which identified salary as a hygiene factor that directly impacts an employee's baseline

job satisfaction. Enhanced compensation, such as higher salaries and better benefits, addresses the fundamental need for financial security and recognition of the value of employees' work. This theory also suggests that the absence of adequate resources can lead to frustration, inefficiency, and dissatisfaction (Herzberg, 1959).

For the informants, improved compensation and resources are essential to maintain their job satisfaction and avoid dissatisfaction. Their desire for higher salaries and better operational support stressed their need to address basic unmet requirements that affect their efficiency and performance.

Enhancing pay scales and providing benefits tailored to the high-risk nature of law enforcement work is necessary to maintain workforce motivation and effectiveness (Kaiser, 2011). While, the availability of operational resources such as equipment, vehicles, and technology is directly linked to the effectiveness of law enforcement agencies. Outdated equipment and insufficient resources compromise officer safety and operational outcomes. Law enforcement personnel often aspire to work in well-resourced environments where they can perform their duties efficiently and safely (Cordner, 2016).

On the other hand, perceived fairness in compensation significantly impacts employee attitudes and behaviors. Law enforcement officers who feel their compensation does not reflect their risks and responsibilities, and they often report dissatisfaction and reduced engagement (Colquitt et al., 2001).

Conclusions

The study concludes that the informants experienced operational risks, work-related stress, and limitations of resources while performing their duties. However, despite the challenges that they encountered, majority of them demonstrated commitment, professionalism, and dedication to public service. They remained committed to serving and fulfilling their mandate in order to create safer communities. They viewed their work as an essential contribution in promoting public safety and security.

The Philippine Drugs Enforcement Agency (PDEA) play a vital role in the fight against the drug problem in the Philippines. Its agents are the frontline personnel who work directly on the ground that carry out operations, investigations and community-based activities. Given the challenges they encountered and the importance of their role, the PDEA agents deserve the recognition and support to continue performing their duties effectively.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

The Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency (PDEA) can reassess the training programs it provides to newly hired personnel. They can formulate specialized training in stress management, ethical decision-making, and self-care practices to strengthen

agents' resilience, mitigate burnout, and ultimately enhance overall performance. Moreover, the agency can refine operational strategies, allocate budgets for financial support during operations, and address manpower and equipment needs to ensure optimal efficiency and effectiveness in their mission.

Moreover, the Dangerous Drugs Board can develop better support systems for the agency. The Office of the President can also support the PDEA by increasing financial support for the agency's operations and funding for essential resources and to improve the welfare of the agents. The Department of Justice (DOJ) can also support the agency on its mandate through conducting a thorough and meticulous evaluation of all witness statements before making any decision to dismiss a case filed by the agency. The lawmakers can revisit existing laws or develop new legislation to better support the agency.

The Local Government Unit, on the other hand, can tailor their own community-based interventions. They can target specific areas, implement targeted education programs, or allocate resources for rehabilitation efforts. Additionally, the barangay officials specifically the Barangay Anti-Drug Abuse Council (BADAC) must be aware of the importance of their role in preventing the spread of prohibited drugs in their community. They must participate actively in local drug prevention and rehabilitation efforts, particularly through the Barangay Drug Clearing Program, which aims to eliminate illegal drug activities at the grassroots level.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The ethical considerations surrounding this study imposed inherent ethical responsibilities to minimize harm and enhance benefits. The beneficence of the study was established through providing an environment where participants felt appreciated and respected for their expertise and experiences. The non-maleficence was addressed by protecting the participants from potential risks such as psychological distress or breaches of confidentiality. Meanwhile, justice was established by representing the diverse perspectives and experiences within the PDEA accurately, avoiding any biases or prejudices that could compromise the integrity of the research findings. While autonomy was determined by obtaining voluntary and informed consent from all participants, clearly explaining the purpose, risks, and benefits of the study, and providing assurances of confidentiality and anonymity.

The bracketing and reflexivity were also established in the conduct of the research. Being an educator in the College of Criminal Justice, the researcher went into this research about the Work Life of the Agents of the Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency (PDEA) with a conscious attempt to abstract from any previous information, experiences, and assumptions that the researcher had. Keeping in mind the possibility that the researcher's experience as a criminologist and an academic teacher might influence the researcher's thinking, the researcher made an effort to dismantle any presuppositions regarding the problems and complexities of the agents' work lives. The researcher put aside any prejudice or anticipations and let the stories of the participants speak for

themselves by means of reflective journaling and active self-monitoring. This process guaranteed the validity of the results as they are embedded in the actual accounts of the PDEA agents and not derived from the researcher's internal comprehension or a certain professional standpoint.

The researcher's academic education and professional experiences in criminology have greatly enhanced the interpretation of the work carried out by Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency (PDEA) agents. This knowledge, however, stressed the importance of the undertaken research as much as the context in which the researcher engaged with it, in particular, the educational role the researcher was to play in describing the experiences of all the participants studied. To counteract this, the researcher was reflexive throughout the research process by analyzing biases and preconceptions to ensure that they did not inhibit the genuine voices of the PDEA agents. The researcher aimed to present an accurate textual representation during the course of the study by encouraging open-mindedness towards the agent's work lives while reflecting in terms of the journal and setting assumptions aside.

The author utilized artificial intelligence (AI) tools to assist in drafting and refining portions of this manuscript. All content has been reviewed, verified, and edited by the author, who assumes full responsibility for the accuracy and integrity of the work.

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REFERENCES

- Bengfort, H. (2024). Employee retention: The real cost of losing an employee. Retrieved December 1, 2024 from <https://www.peoplekeep.com/blog/employee-retention-the-real-cost-of-losing-an-employee>.
- Cebu Daily News. (2024). Bohol: Shabu worth P172.7M seized in 14 months. Retrieved April 10, 2024 from <https://cebudailynews.inquirer.net/561089/bohol-shabu-worth-p172-7m-seized-in-14-months>.
- Clingan, P. (2020). Types of stress impacts critical thinking skills, sleep, and job-related performance in law enforcement: A literature review. Retrieved December 12, 2024 from https://www.academia.edu/111582615/Types_of_Stress_Impacts_Critical_Thinking_Skills_Sleep_and_Job_Related_Performance_in_Law_Enforcement_A_Literature_Review.
- Colquitt, J. A., Conlon, D. E., Wesson, M. J., Porter, C. O. & Ng, K. Y. (2001). Justice at the millennium: A meta-analytic review of 25 years of organizational justice research. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 86(3), 425-445.
- Cordner, G. (2016). *Police administration: Structures, processes, and behavior*. Routledge.
- Damuag, E., Sayson, Y., Sabijon, D., Boniao, G., Tano, A., Abasa, L. & Alcontin, M. (2024). Experiences of drug surrenderees in highly urbanized cities in Cebu: A phenomenological study. *International Journal of Law and Politics Studies*, 6(3), 32-44. <https://doi.org/10.32996/ijlps.2024.6.3.3>.
- Engetou, M. (2017). Impact of insufficient personnel on organizational performance. Retrieved March 9, 2024 from <https://www.theseus.fi/handle/10024/141344>.
- Fuentes, B., Gengania, J., Malon, K., Mayol, K., Allanic, E. & Cuevas, F., Jr. (2023). Lived experiences of police officers in the implementation of operational plan against illegal drugs. *Mediterranean Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences (MJBAS)*, 7(3), 34-47.
- Gadirajurrett, H., Srinivasan, R., Stevens, J. & Jeena, N. (2018). Impact of leadership on team's performance. *Portland State University PDXScholar*.
- Gerber, J. F. & O'Neill, K. (2012). Police career development: Factors influencing job satisfaction and retention. *Police Practice and Research*, 13(4), 288-298.
- Hackman, J. R. (2002). *Leading teams: Setting the stage for great performances*. Harvard Business School Press.

- Harter, S. (1978). Effectance motivation reconsidered: Toward a developmental model. *Human Development*, 21(1), 34-64.
- Herzberg, F. (1959). *The motivation to work*. New York, NY: John Wiley & Sons.
- Herzberg, F. (1966). *Work and the nature of man*. World Publishing Company.
- Humphrey, S., Morgeson, F. & Mannor, M. (2009). Developing a theory of the strategic core of teams: A role composition model of team performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 94(1), 48–61.
- Iyer, Y. (2022). Herzberg's two-factor theory in project management. Retrieved December 4, 2024 from <https://www.wrike.com/blog/what-is-herzbergs-two-factor-theory/>.
- Jelinek, J. (2024). How to keep work stress from taking over your life. Retrieved December 6, 2024 from <https://www.healthline.com/health/work-stress>.
- Kaiser, R. B. (2011). The impact of compensation on law enforcement retention and performance. *Public Administration Review*, 71(5), 689-698.
- Kappeler, V. E. & Gaines, L. K. (2012). *Community policing: A contemporary perspective*. Pearson Higher Ed.
- Laila, M. (2021). The role of the Medan police in law enforcement of criminal acts of narcotics. *Journal of Law Science*. 3(4), 164-175. <https://doi.org/10.35335/jls.v3i4.1689>.
- Lamchek, J. & Jopson, T. (2024). Confronting the Philippines' war on drugs: A literature review. *Sociology Compass*. 18(5), 134-145. <https://doi.org/10.1111/soc4.13209>.
- Meliton, C. (2016). The role and arrest powers of officers deputized for federal drug enforcement. Retrieved April 10, 2024 from <https://www.proquest.com/openview/15c8d07ef12ccd38aa49103ff763e89d/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750>.
- Noble, P. S. (2024). Lived experiences of Philippine National Police drug enforcers in the Eastern Visayas Region. *Journal Asia Pacific Journal of Advanced Education and Technology*. 3(3), 11-123. <https://doi.org/10.54476/apjaet/32469>.
- Petrocelli, M., Oberweis, T., Smith, M. & Petrocelli, J. (2014). Assessing police attitudes toward drugs and drug enforcement. Retrieved June 17, 2024 from <https://doi.org/10.1007/S12103-013-9200-Z>.
- Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency [PDEA]. (n.d.). Republic Act 9165. Retrieved April 10, 2024 from <https://pdea.gov.ph/laws-and-regulationsrepublic-act-9165>.
- Philippine News Agency [PNA]. (2024). 5.7K high-value targets nabbed under Marcos admin's drug drive. Retrieved October 15, 2024 from <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1222306>.
- Queiros, C., Passos, F., Bartolo, A., Faria, S., Fonseca, S., Marques, A., Silva, C. & Pereira, A. (2020). Job stress, burnout and coping in police officers: Relationships and psychometric properties of the organizational police stress questionnaire. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 17(18). doi: 10.3390/ijerph17186718.
- Sutton, J. (2021). Workplace stress management: 11 best strategies & worksheets. Retrieved December 12, 2024 from <https://positivepsychology.com/workplace-stress-management/>.
- The Bohol Tribune. (2024). P714,000 worth of shabu seized from top drug pusher in Bohol. Retrieved April 10, 2024 from

- <https://theboholtribune.com/2024/02/18/p714000-worth-of-shabu-zeized-from-top-drug-pusher-in-bohol/>.
- Tupas, E. (2019). PDEA chief admits receiving death threats. Retrieved December 01, 2024 from <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2019/07/08/1932963/pdea-chief-admits-receiving-death-threats>.
- United Nation [UN]. (2023). World drug report 2023. Retrieved December 05, 2024 from <https://www.unodc.org/unodc/data-and-analysis/world-drug-report-2023.html>.
- United Nations [UN]. (2024). United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) world drug report 2024: Harms of world drug problem continue to mount amid expansions in drug use and markets. Retrieved December 12, 2024 from <https://www.unodc.org/unodc/data-and-analysis/world-drug-report-2024.html>.
- Van der Hoek, M., Groeneveld, S. & Kuipers, B. (2016). Goal setting in teams: Goal clarity and team performance in the public sector. Retrieved December 12, 2024 from <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6207990/>.